

Leading Against the Grain: Exploring the Leadership Career Pathways of Women in Career and Technical Education

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Abstract

This study examines the nonlinear and often serendipitous leadership trajectories of women in Career and Technical Education (CTE), exploring how intersectional identities shape their career decisions, leadership emergence, and persistence. Drawing on phenomenological interviews with women leaders and surveys of students in workforce development programs, the study reveals core themes such as reluctant but purposeful leadership, the influence of mentorship, and systemic barriers, including pay inequity and institutional undervaluing of CTE. Initial findings point to critical gaps in leadership development and representation. The goal is to construct a leadership framework grounded in lived experience that advances gender equity, expands leadership capacity, and informs institutional strategies in CTE settings.

Keywords: female, career and technical education, leadership

Introduction

Women remain underrepresented in leadership positions across educational contexts, and this disparity is particularly pronounced in the field of Career and Technical Education (CTE). While women's enrollment in CTE programs has increased, their advancement into leadership roles remains limited. National data show that although women now make up a significant proportion of the workforce in higher education, they continue to be underrepresented in executive positions, especially in fields traditionally dominated by men (American Council on Education, 2022). Even as more women assume leadership in postsecondary institutions, where they help drive gender equity and reform, persistent structural and cultural barriers still impede career advancement. This phenomenon is shaped by intersecting factors, including the marginal status of CTE within academia, deeply rooted gender norms, and organizational practices that restrict access to formal leadership pipelines.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in Intersectionality Theory, which conceptualizes how interlocking identities such as gender, race, and socioeconomic status combine to shape individuals' experiences and access to power (Crenshaw, 1989; Collins, 2015). This lens allows the research to account for the compound nature of barriers faced by women in CTE leadership, especially those from underrepresented backgrounds. Further, Transformational Leadership Theory (Bass, 1985) is used, as it emphasizes the importance of motivation, individualized support, and role modeling as key leadership strategies.

Purpose and Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to investigate how women in CTE ascend to leadership positions, what influences their pathways, and what structural or interpersonal factors affect their leadership capacity. This study aims to address the following research questions:

1. How do women in CTE describe the development of their leadership identities and careers?
2. What barriers and supports do they encounter as they move into and through leadership roles?
3. How do current female students in workforce-related programs perceive leadership opportunities and challenges?
4. What insights can inform the development of an inclusive leadership framework for postsecondary CTE?

Methods and Procedures

This mixed-methods study uses a phenomenological approach to gather and interpret the lived experiences of women in CTE leadership. Qualitative data collection involved in-depth, semi-structured interviews with a purposive sample of three women who currently hold leadership roles in postsecondary or workforce-focused CTE positions (Moustakas, 1994; Creswell & Poth, 2018). Participants were selected based on their eligibility as female CTE leaders. One-hour interviews were conducted virtually to ensure convenience and geographic flexibility. Interview questions focused on leadership emergence, career decision-making, mentorship, and systemic challenges.

In parallel, a survey was distributed to current students enrolled in CTE and Career and Workforce Education (CWE) programs at a public doctoral university in Florida. The survey captured early career perceptions of leadership, confidence levels, perceived barriers, and desired support mechanisms. A total of 13 student responses were collected, 12 student responses were used. Responses were primarily from graduate students.

Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was used to code and categorize the qualitative interview data, identifying recurring themes and insights. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze quantitative survey items and provide insights into trends and distributions within the student sample (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval and ethical standards guided all research activities to ensure participant confidentiality and research integrity.

In addition to qualitative interviews and student survey responses, a supplemental content analysis was conducted using publicly available information from the Advance CTE website (<https://careertech.org/about/state-directors/>). A list of state and territorial CTE directors as of July 2025 was reviewed to examine gender representation across leadership roles. Because the website does not list self-identified gender, an informed but subjective inference was made based on names and publicly available biographical details (e.g., pronouns, photographs, or institutional bios where applicable). While this introduces the possibility of misclassification bias, it allowed for a general descriptive analysis of gender distribution in state-level CTE leadership.

Preliminary Findings

An analysis of state and territorial Career and Technical Education (CTE) leadership reveals that, as of July 2025, women occupy a majority of state director

positions. Of the 52 roles reviewed, 31 directors were inferred to be female (approximately 60%), while 21 were inferred to be male (approximately 40%).

Table 1

Gender Distribution of State CTE Directors

Gender Number of Directors Percentage

Female	31	59.6%
Male	21	40.4%
Total	52	100%

Note. Gender was inferred from publicly available information and may not reflect self-identified gender. Data were collected from the Advance CTE directory in July 2025.

Interview and survey findings are summarized separately below.

Table 2

Interview Themes: Leadership Pathways Among Women in CTE

Theme	Description
Nonlinear Pathways	Leadership journeys shaped by external events and chance opportunities.
Reluctant but Purpose-Driven	Participants lead with intentionality despite initial hesitation.
Mentorship as Catalyst	Mentors expanded participants’ leadership aspirations and confidence.
Gendered Expectations	Cultural and familial expectations constrained early career choices.
Institutional Barriers	Undervaluing of CTE, pay gaps, and lack of tenure pathways were cited.
National Networks	Fellowships and associations elevated leadership visibility.
Burnout and Boundaries	Balancing leadership and family requires deliberate effort.
Pay Inequity	Participants identified gendered disparities in compensation.
Advocacy for Women	Leaders emphasized mentorship and visibility to support others.
Student-Centered Success	Success defined by student achievement and growth.
Systemic Neglect	Leadership prep programs overlook CTE as a leadership discipline.

Survey Results: Perceptions from CTE/CWE Students

Table 3

Summary of Student Responses on Leadership Confidence, Barriers, and Support

Needs (N = 12)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Leadership Confidence		
Very confident	3	25%
Moderately confident	6	50%
Slightly confident	3	25%
Perceived Leadership Opportunity		
Yes	6	50%
No	6	50%
Awareness of Leadership Dev. Resources		
Not aware at all	3	25%
Slightly aware	4	33.3%
Moderately aware	4	33.3%
Very much aware	1	8.3%
Preferred Leadership Focus Area		
Teaching and training	4	33.3%
Advocacy and community engagement	4	33.3%
Administration and policy	2	16.7%
Industry leadership	1	8.3%
Unsure	1	8.3%
Overall Program Satisfaction		
Extremely satisfied	1	8.3%
Somewhat satisfied	4	33.3%
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	4	33.3%
Somewhat dissatisfied	1	8.3%
Not reported	2	16.7%

Table 4

Survey Themes: Perceptions from CTE/CWE Students

Theme	Description
Leadership Confidence	Most students reported moderate confidence, with desire for growth.
Limited Engagement	Few students held leadership roles, citing lack of exposure/opportunities.
Influential Factors	Coursework, work experience, and personal interest were key.
Barriers to Leadership	Gender bias, low confidence, family demands, and limited visibility.
Support Needs	Mentorship, peer groups, networking, and funding for basic needs.
Awareness	Many students are unaware of existing leadership development opportunities.
Preferred Focus Areas	Interests varied: teaching, advocacy, policy, and industry leadership.

Table 5

Overlapping Themes: Interview and Survey Participants

Shared Theme	Evidence of Overlap
Mentorship Gaps	Both groups emphasized the need for accessible and meaningful mentors.
Gendered Barriers	Women cited bias, pay gaps, and male-dominated environments.
Leadership Confidence	Students and leaders alike expressed evolving self-perceptions.
Burnout and Balance	Time constraints, caregiving, and workload stress were common.
Limited Visibility	Participants noted the underrepresentation of women in leadership.
Advocacy and Representation	Both groups viewed representation as critical to inclusion.

Preliminary Discussion

In addition to qualitative interviews and student surveys, a gender audit was conducted using publicly available information from Advance CTE’s State Director directory (July 2025). A total of 52 state and territorial CTE director roles were analyzed. The results show that:

- **31 of 52** directors were inferred to be female ($\approx 60\%$)
- **21 of 52** were inferred to be male ($\approx 40\%$)

These preliminary findings are noteworthy given broader trends of gender underrepresentation in education leadership, particularly in technical and workforce-related fields. The apparent gender parity in CTE state leadership signals progress but also invites deeper analysis of representation quality. Because gender was inferred based on publicly available names and biographical details, and not self-reported, these findings reflect approximations. Still, they offer a valuable glimpse into trends at the leadership level.

Regional patterns suggest that women hold director positions across diverse parts of the country, including the West (e.g., California, Oregon, Washington), Northeast (e.g., Massachusetts, Connecticut, New York), South (e.g., Georgia, Louisiana, Texas), and Midwest (e.g., Michigan, Nebraska). Male directors were more prominently observed in some Southern and rural states, indicating potential regional and cultural differences in leadership access and selection.

Governance structures also reveal interesting dynamics: women appear more frequently in states where CTE is governed by departments of education, while

workforce board–governed structures trend more male. Although tenure data were not available, national patterns suggest that many women may be newer appointees, entering leadership through evolving equity initiatives rather than long-standing succession plans.

Interview and Survey

The preliminary findings of this study illuminate the complex, intersecting challenges women face in navigating leadership within CTE. While participants' experiences reveal strong commitments to student-centered equity and reform, their trajectories also underscore persistent structural and cultural barriers that shape leadership access and sustainability. These experiences align with the concept of the leadership labyrinth, which recognizes that women's advancement is not obstructed by a single barrier, but rather a series of interwoven obstacles across contexts and time (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Additionally, these data reflect intersectional dynamics where gendered experiences of leadership are further complicated by race, class, and caregiving roles (Crenshaw, 1989; Collins, 2015).

Navigating the Leadership Labyrinth in CTE

The integration of state-level data challenges some assumptions about women's underrepresentation in leadership. While women now occupy the majority of state CTE director positions, this visibility does not necessarily reflect depth, stability, or equity of opportunity. For instance, many women may be recent appointees with limited institutional support, still navigating systems historically built for, and by, male leaders. This paradox of numerical presence without systemic change reinforces Eagly and Carli's (2007) metaphor of the leadership labyrinth.

Intersectionality

The apparent parity in CTE state leadership may mask underlying disparities in race, tenure, and institutional power. The female leaders in this study, like many women of color or first-generation professionals in leadership, still report significant barriers including tokenization, pay inequity, and lack of advancement pathways. Crenshaw's (1989) theory of intersectionality is especially relevant here, as it illustrates how multiple marginalized identities compound leadership challenges even in spaces where women are numerically present.

Mentorship and Leadership Identity Formation

Both interview and survey participants consistently identified mentorship as a catalyst for leadership development, yet access to meaningful mentorship remained uneven. This echoes Eagly and Carli's (2007) assertion that women benefit significantly from developmental relationships but face systemic barriers to acquiring them especially in male-dominated disciplines. The absence of diverse, visible mentors not only limits skill development but also hinders leadership identity formation. As students and leaders alike expressed, the lack of representation reinforced self-doubt and uncertainty, confirming prior findings that visibility is essential to inclusion and advancement in leadership (Bass, 1985; NCWGE, 2021).

Performative Mentorship as a Barrier. Even as female leaders rise in number, their experiences are not uniformly positive. The state-level data show quantity, but qualitative interviews reveal quality gaps in mentorship, leadership development, and cultural support. Performative mentorship, highlighted by one participant, emerges as a critical theme. It underscores the need to distinguish between symbolic inclusion (i.e., representation) and substantive inclusion (i.e., agency, investment, and opportunity).

The Burden of Burnout and Boundary-Making

Burnout emerged as a recurring theme, often tied to overextension and emotional labor hallmarks of the leadership labyrinth for women balancing professional, personal, and caregiving roles (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Participants described creating boundaries as a form of resistance and sustainability, yet few institutional structures supported these efforts. The intersectional pressure to perform flawlessly while navigating systemic bias contributes to what Collins (2015) frames as the “outsider-within” experience: belonging just enough to bear the burden, but rarely enough to share in the power.

Broadening the Conversation on Representation

The presence of women in 60% of CTE state director roles should not end the conversation; it should deepen it. Which women are being elevated? Are they supported once in office? Do their roles influence policy, budget, and culture? These questions push the field beyond celebration and into accountability, where success is not just about how many women lead, but how well they are equipped to thrive and bring others with them.

Toward Intersectional Leadership Development

The overlapping themes between current leaders and aspiring students point to a larger ecosystem of exclusion and potential transformation. The findings suggest a pressing need for leadership development frameworks that acknowledge the labyrinthine nature of leadership progression and the intersectional identities of those navigating it. These frameworks must dismantle structural barriers, center mentorship and visibility, and advocate for institutional policies that reflect the lived realities of women in CTE.

Proposed Framework: Intersectional Leadership Development in CTE

Drawing from the preliminary themes and findings of this study, a proposed leadership development framework is offered to address the unique and overlapping needs of women in CTE. This framework integrates intersectionality and transformational leadership principles to guide future interventions and institutional practices.

1. **Mentorship and Sponsorship Networks**
 - Develop formal mentoring structures with emphasis on representation and shared identity.
 - Incorporate both peer and upward mentorship models to broaden access.
2. **Leadership Visibility and Curriculum Integration**
 - Integrate leadership development and CTE-specific equity modules into coursework.
 - Include case studies and historical contributions of women in CTE to normalize female leadership.
3. **Institutional Support and Policy Reform**

- Advocate for equity-based performance evaluation and promotion systems.
 - Support flexible leadership pathways that accommodate diverse life experiences.
4. **Professional Development and Leadership Pipelines**
 - Facilitate conference participation, national fellowships, and leadership academies.
 - Identify and remove barriers to faculty advancement in CTE disciplines.
 5. **Monitoring and Reflective Practice**
 - Use data to track participation, advancement, and satisfaction among female CTE students and leaders.
 - Implement feedback loops to continually adapt leadership programming to changing needs.

Recommendations

Based on the preliminary findings and proposed framework, the recommendations are as follows:

1. Postsecondary institutions should create targeted leadership development programs for women in CTE, integrating meaningful mentorship and career mapping.
2. CTE programs should enhance visibility and celebration of women's contributions, through speaker series, historical curriculum modules, and national CTE campaigns.
3. Professional associations should expand support for early-career leadership development, especially for women from historically underrepresented groups.
4. Policy leaders and funders should prioritize CTE equity in state and national leadership frameworks, ensuring women have structural access to advancement.
5. Faculty and administrators must advocate for structural inclusion of CTE in institutional leadership planning, including pathways to tenure, promotion, and executive roles.
6. Future research should continue exploring intersectional identities in leadership to address nuanced experiences and scalable solutions.

These recommendations aim to cultivate a more equitable, visible, and supportive leadership culture for women in Career and Technical Education.

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